

DIAGNOSTIC METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL AND ETHICAL COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS IN THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8142879>

Abstract. *This article highlights the importance of the diagnostic methodology for the development of professional and ethical competence of primary school teachers and the uniqueness of changing diagnostic analyzes based on today's demands.*

Keywords: *diagnostic, competent, professional-ethical, periodic process, attitude, experience-test, entry level, correctional level, final level*

The periodic process of organizing professional development aimed at the development of professional and ethical competence envisages its construction on a diagnostic basis. Taking into account the need to evaluate the effectiveness of the experimental test, diagnostic support consists of three levels (stages) and includes the following:

1. *Introduction level.* The level of interest of the listeners in the field of professional and ethical competence and the level of preparation for its development is an entrance diagnosis.
2. *Correctional level.* Gradual correction of the results obtained during the training process.
3. *The final level.* Final assessment of the effectiveness of the integrative model of the development of the professional and moral competence of the primary school teacher in the process of professional development.

The basis of the entire process of diagnostics is the teacher's readiness to study in the process of professional development, his desire to solve the important problems (difficulties) of his professional and ethical competence, and his positive ideas about achieving concrete goals of personal importance.

We consider the teacher's difficulties in the field of professional-ethical competence as indicators of the educational needs of the primary school teacher, because professional difficulties are considered a specific "obstacle" for further professional-ethical development. They regulate the teacher's professional behavior, thinking, will and feelings, because they are expressed in the situation where a person feels the need for certain knowledge and skills necessary for the teacher's professional and ethical realization and development. Since the process of meeting educational needs serves as a purposeful activity of the teacher, educational needs are the sources of the teacher's activity. The direction of diagnostic support is to reveal, evaluate and develop the teacher's internal professional and ethical capabilities, and to change the level of his qualification.

In this regard, the main tasks of diagnostic support are diagnostics of the following:

- professional and ethical experience;
- the teacher's professional and ethical activity, his motives, successes, problems, their causes, the orientation of the teacher's educational needs;
- elimination of various professional difficulties of the teacher in the process of professional

development;

- the effectiveness of the events and the general training process.

We distinguish three operational stages of diagnostic support for the development of the professional and ethical competence of the primary school teacher during the training process.

1) diagnosis of professional and ethical experience based on the development of professional and ethical competence of the pedagogue and identification of difficulties in self-assessment of its level (collaborative activities of andragogue and teacher);

2) diagnosis of teacher overcoming professional difficulties;

3) evaluation of the efficiency of development of professional and ethical competence during the training process based on the implementation of the integrative model.

At the *first stage* of diagnostic support, we suggest using the methodology “*Updating the previous professional and ethical experience of the teacher*” to determine the teacher's difficulties in the field of professional and ethical competence and its level, as well as his interest in improving his skills in this field. It is based on the idea of actualization, i.e. transfer of accumulated professional and ethical experience (competence) to a potential state.

In this context, the teacher's professional and ethical experience is expressed in the following:

a) in the set of knowledge, skills, qualifications and methods of upbringing and education acquired in the process of professional education and practice;

b) as a result of the teacher's creative, spiritual-ethical search for the formation of appropriate basic professional-ethical personality qualities (in accordance with the structure of professional-ethical competence), that is:

- confidence in the child's strength and capabilities;

- interest in the inner world of children;

- openness to accept other views, points of view;

- common culture and value orientation;

- emotional stability;

- positive orientation to pedagogical activity. Self-confidence.

Actualization of professional-ethical experience allows the teacher to remember its features and use it in the future diagnostic process, which identifies advantages and difficulties in the teacher's professional-ethical activity.

The indicated method of diagnostic support (identification of professional difficulties and search for ways to solve these difficulties) has an educational orientation for the teacher. In this case, professional development and, accordingly, the development of professional and ethical competence will have a personal orientation, because the teacher becomes a center of diagnostic observation, the subject of the educational process with equal rights with the teacher-andragogue. This stage is based on the self-diagnosis of the teacher's professional and ethical competence. In this way, the potential effect of professional development occurs, because the teacher's reflection leads to his knowledge of his professional-ethical experience, understanding it in terms of identified professional-personal advantages and disadvantages.

In the *second stage* of diagnostic observation, the development of the professional and moral competence of the primary school teacher is carried out with the diagnosis of the teacher's overcoming of the identified difficulties. Based on the information received during education, the teacher is invited to independently evaluate his professional and ethical knowledge and skills and

to create his “professional and ethical direction” again. For this, the andragogic determines which professional difficulties have been solved in the teacher’s opinion (on the basis of the evaluation form “Professional-Ethical Orientation”).

1) Suggests to the teacher to rate the degree of solving the difficulty from 1 to 5 points:

1 point - the difficulty is not sufficiently resolved, there are many more questions that an andragogic can help me solve;

2 points - the difficulty is not sufficiently solved, there are several questions that an andragogic can help me solve;

3 points - the difficulty is solved satisfactorily, there are several issues that cause difficulties in my growth, but I can solve them independently;

4 points - the difficulty is solved and does not raise questions;

5 points - the difficulty is solved and does not raise questions, allows you to clearly see the professional perspective.

The higher the score that determines the level of professional-ethical problem solving by the teacher, the higher the quality of the educational process aimed at developing the professional-ethical competence of the primary school teacher.

My difficulties and their solution

Listener _____

Description of difficulties	Scores indicating the level of professional-ethical problem solving	Quality of educational process, %
1.	1 2 3 4 5	20 40 60 80 100
2. and etc		

An increase in the teacher's assessment of his professional skills, which were previously underestimated, is a positive result of teacher education. In the unchanged evaluation of his professional skills by the teacher, he is offered to find the reasons for this situation, which may be in the teacher himself or in the organization of the training process. All sides of the process - teacher and andragogist - should actively participate in this analytical work.

The comparative analysis of all the factors and results of the diagnosis serves as the basis for the conclusions about the effectiveness of the implementation of the integrative model of the development of the professional and moral competence of the primary school teacher during the training process obtained within the framework of two diagnostic stages.

In this case, the level of achievement of the teaching result as a personal growth in the formation and development of the teacher's professional and ethical qualities serves as a criterion of efficiency. In addition, as an additional evaluation criterion, the student's assessment of the level of compliance with the problem of professional-ethical competence development as an indicator of the overall efficiency of the educational process or the level of compliance (organization, content, result) of the courses with the goals of professional-ethical development serves.

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